

IMPROVEMENT OF INNOVATIVE AND INTEGRATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

Berdikulova Nasiba Erkinjonovna

Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Annotation: The introduction of integration into the education system can become a key tool in solving educational and educational tasks between the school and society. Integrated lessons teach children to understand from nature that they understand the unity of the worldview, the continuity of events. It should also be borne in mind that the integration links of classes in primary school are poorly developed scientifically. And since the various ideas and views that exist are contradictory and contradictory, the problem of integration is still one of the controversial issues among our acquisitions.

Keywords: interconnection of sciences, specified objects, innovative technologies

The development of the theory of the application of integration in the pedagogical process is a competition of scientific and pedagogical concepts, basic and important. Integration is inextricably linked with differentiation. This harmony is manifested in the restoration of the system of their desire to understand the knowledge they receive in students. Integration is the convergence and interconnection of sciences in the process of differentiation. The integration process is a stage of connecting the interrelations between disciplines in a new, higher quality, manifested in a higher form. It should be noted that the integration process is based on folk pedagogy and scientific pedagogy of the distant past.

In the coverage of the content of each subject, its essence is formed by the teacher for the purpose of deep, scientifically grounded imagination of students, productive use of time, wide coverage of the possibilities of applying their theoretical knowledge in practice, in everyday life and production, expansion of their polytechnic ideas, and is expressed in a calendar-thematic plan.

The content of the sciences of primary education through the comprehensive improvement of teaching:

- to create monitoring of the level of knowledge acquisition and spiritual formation of students;

- constant monitoring of the extent to which the knowledge given by teachers is mastered by students; - ensuring consistency and continuity in the formation of the spirituality of the student's personality in the process of primary education;

In technology lessons, students will need concepts such as right angles, perpendicular and parallel lines, right triangles and a rectangular rectangle to form shapes. In addition, students will have to determine the angles of a part or object, the centers of arcs, other dimensions of a straight and curved line using various tools, such as the axis of symmetry, symmetrical drawing of shapes, a circle making attempts, a donut, a donut, an angle ruler, a circle, for labor lessons. In such times, sciences related to geometry will be needed. Consequently, in the school geometry course there are great opportunities for performing such works as the use of drawing and measuring tools, the replacement of surfaces. The challenge is to use them intelligently in work lessons. Also, knowledge of arithmetic is necessary when performing such works as determining the length of specified objects, feed, height, surface, volume, as well as various sizes, calculating how much material will be spent time. The term "innovation" is defined differently in encyclopedias and dictionaries. In a large encyclopedic dictionary, this concept is interpreted as a neoplasm. The Soviet Encyclopedic dictionary also defines it as a new formation. A.I. Kochetov gives the concept of "innovation" the following definitions: a holistic theoretical and technological and methodological concept of updating pedagogical activity, ensuring its output to the specified level. We cannot fully agree with this definition. In the opinion of V. Kvash and V. Latkina "innovation is the creation of fundamentally new patterns of activity that go beyond the norm, unregulated, bringing professional activity to a fundamentally new qualitative level." Practice convinces that any innovation goes beyond the normalized activity and is aimed at a breakthrough forward. But at the same time, the teaching staff of

innovative schools needs to look back at past experience, correlate their activities with existing practice.

Since six- to seven-year-olds mostly prefer verbal communication, the teacher should give them the opportunity to talk about mathematics with the help of questions. Such questions can be such as: "Tell us how you imagine it" or "Can you explain how you understand it?". At the same time, it is necessary:

- involve more students in the discussion.
- Write down the answer on the blackboard or on a large piece of paper.
- Invite the class to express the students' answers in different ways.
- Try not to give solutions that mean the end of the discussion.

The educational objectives of the "Step by step" program in mathematics can be divided into 6 types according to content: pictures and ratios, the sense of number and numbering, the concept of operations with integers, geometry and the meaning of space, measurements, statistics and probability.

Studying the problems of using innovative teaching technologies in mathematics lessons, based on the experience of primary school teachers in Uzbekistan, it can be seen that in response to the increasing demands of the school to the personality of primary school students, to their level of development, the most progressive part of teachers is trying to optimize the educational process through the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies.

All of the above allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. In our opinion, the use of innovative technologies of teaching and upbringing in mathematics lessons in primary school contributes to the activation of the educational process, allows us to develop positive internal motivation of learning, namely: students experience moral satisfaction, high emotional mood, joy of experiencing success.

2. Planning, developing and working out the most favorable background of intensive learning in mathematics lessons contributes to positive changes in the personal, motivational and semantic sphere of the student.

It would be advisable to use innovative teaching technologies more widely in mathematics lessons, as they increase interest in the subject being studied, as well as develop students' mental abilities more deeply.

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